

ENF TEST SIMULATION OF STITCHED COMPOSITES BASED ON SHEAR TESTING RESULTS OF SINGLE STITCHED LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, an experimental and numerical method was conducted to investigate single stitched laminates under pure shear loading. The experimental set-up consisted of standard Iosipescu fixture with additional clamping system to hold the specimen during the test, and the test results were used to verify related numerical simulation. The numerical model adopts spring connector to represent the stitch thread. Furthermore, end notch flexural (ENF) simulation was developed based on single stitch model, and cohesive zone model (CZM) was used to simulate the crack propagation. Finally, the ENF simulation showed strong agreement with the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Stitching is one of 3D reinforcement techniques that developed to suppress the delamination propagation in composite laminates. The technique is done by inserting threads into the preforms in through-thickness direction. It has been proved that stitching can increase significantly the delamination resistance of composite laminates under mode I [1-3] and mode II [4-7].

To quantify the efficiency of delamination suppression, the crack bridging mechanism by the stitch threads has to be understood. In case of mode I, the bridging mechanism was clearly investigated [3]. However in case of mode II, the bridging mechanisms are remained unclear due to the difficulties to investigate visually the crack propagation and stitch thread deformation during the ENF test. Based on our literature review, the first work on stitch bridging mechanism was reported by Cox et.al [8]. The experimental and analytical study of single stitched laminates under mode II loading was reported. The authors noted that further study was needed to understand the detailed stitch plasticity, rupture and pull-out process. Also, the detailed experimental set-up of single stitched laminate was not described explicitly. Chen et.al [9] conducted single stitched laminate testing under pure shear test and reported that the interaction of stitch thread with surrounding laminates during shear loading was elastic-perfectly plastic. This interaction was applied to the finite element model to predict the energy release rate of stitched composites using J-integral contour method.

A new testing method of single stitched laminate was proposed by our group [10]. A modified Iosipescu fixture was used with additional holder to clamp the specimen during the test. The force-displacement curve obtained by interlaminar shear test (IST) of single stitch specimen was adopted to simulate the ENF testing. This paper is addressed to check the repeatability of the proposed method using different in-plane laminates orientations.

2 INTERLAMINAR SHEAR TEST (IST) OF SINGLE STITCHED LAMINATES

2.1 Materials preparation and testing method

Interlaminar shear test (IST) specimens were cut from the composite laminates based on Fig. 1. The stitched composite laminates were made by carbon fibres T800SC-24 (Toray Industry), RTM-6

epoxy (Hexcel) as the matrix, and Vectran (Kuraray) as the stitch thread. The laminates contained 20-ply with orientation: $[45/90/-45/0/0/45/90/90/-45/0]_s$ which was different with the previous work [10]. Stitch threads of 500 Denier (equal to 0.0394 mm^2 of cross-sectional area) were inserted into the preform followed by consolidation process using resin transfer moulding (RTM).

Figure 1: Geometry of IST specimen

There are nine stitch threads positions in one specimen, each position consisted of two stitch threads. All of stitch threads which are laid along the edges were cut exactly at the release film position using thin and sharp razor. Only stitch threads at the centre was remained, then the specimen was hold with special clamping system that has been designed to be fit with standard Iosipescu fixture as shown in Fig. 2. Finally, pure shear test with modified Iosipescu fixture was conducted using tensile test machine (Instron series 4505). A small load cell with max 10kN load was used with cross head speed of 0.025 mm/min.

Figure 2: Interlaminar shear test set-up

2.2 Finite element modelling of interlaminar shear test

All the modelling techniques in previous work [10] were adopted. The laminate properties for this typical work are shown in Table 1. Noted that the loading direction (x -axis) is along the resin rich region as shown in Fig. 3, which is different with the case of delamination at interlaminar $90^\circ/90^\circ$ [10]. To address this issue, the matrix properties are applied for the area surrounding the stitch thread.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
158.6	4.7	4.7	3.8	3.8	2.7	0.33	0.33	0.47

Table 1: Laminate's properties used in simulation

Figure 3: Interface of laminates mid layer

3 END NOTCH FLEXURAL (ENF) TEST

3.1 ENF EXPERIMENT

The specimen preparation and experimental set-up (Fig. 4) followed the procedures in our previous work [7]. The differences are in the total number of plies and laminates orientation, as mentioned above. In order to validate the finite element simulation results, the experimental tests were conducted continuously till the cracks reach the center of loading pin. Noted that in the previous work [7], the test was stopped immediately when the crack start to propagate, and followed by unloading. Tabbed end notch flexural (TENF) specimens were used to avoid premature failure of the laminates before the crack propagates to the center of loading point.

Figure 4: Experimental set-up of tabbed end notch flexural test [7]

3.2 ENF SIMULATION

Cohesive zone modeling (CZM) was used to simulate crack propagations. It was recommended [10] to use interface stiffness within the range 4.25×10^{14} till $4.5 \times 10^{14} \text{ N/m}^3$, and viscosity coefficient of cohesive element between 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} . The geometry modelling is shown in Fig. 5, and detailed cohesive zone parameters used in this work are summarized in Table 2.

K_0 (N/m^3)	σ_I^o (MPa)	σ_{II}^o (MPa)	σ_{III}^o (MPa)	G_s^c (J/m^2)	G_t^c (J/m^2)	α
4.25×10^{14}	40	70	70	450	800	1

Table 2: Cohesive zone parameters

Figure 5: Geometry of TENF model

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Interlaminar shear test

The experimental and numerical simulation results of interlaminar shear test are shown in Fig. 6. The experimental results showed non-linear curve before the displacement reaches 0.5 mm. This non-linear part expressed the delamination process at the mid layers. Although the film has been inserted at mid layers, significant forces are still needed to complete the delamination. To confirm this issue, some trials have also been conducted without pre-crack with sharp razor, and huge force was needed to create delamination (the release film could not work at all). Compared to reported work on 3D reinforcement using Z-pin [11], almost no extra force needed to create delamination that proved the film works properly. In Z-pin case, the laminates are manufactured from prepreg. The released film is inserted between prepreg followed by Z-pin insertion. On the other hand, in case of stitched composites the release film is inserted into the pre-form, followed by stitching and pre-tension of the fibers. This manufacturing process of stitched laminates influences the flatness of the inserted film. Some damages on the release film cannot be avoided due to insertion of stitch thread, and those damages could be propagated during resin transfer molding (RTM) process. Furthermore, Fig. 7 exhibited the fracture surface of IST. In some areas, the delamination were happened at film interface, but in some other areas were not.

Considering the curve shape after the specimen delaminated completely, the properties of spring connector (used to represent the stitch thread) is assumed to be linear. The finite element simulation result of IST is presented in Fig. 6.

In addition to the issue of release film effectiveness, further works are also needed to verify clearly the bridging mechanism of the stitch thread, so that the energy dissipated by the stitch deformation and fracture can be predicted.

4.2 ENF testing and simulation results

The load displacement curve of typical experimental test and related finite element simulation results are shown in Fig. 8. Finite element results have strong agreement with the experimental one for both steps, before and after crack propagation. Therefore, the FE results confirmed that the techniques and parameters used in finite element modeling in the previous work [10] are also applicable for another laminates orientations and thickness.

Figure 6: Experimental and numerical results of IST

Figure 7: Fracture surface of IST

Figure 8: Experimental and numerical results of ENF test

9 CONCLUSIONS

This work has confirmed the repeatability of modelling techniques of stitched composites under mode II loading (ENF test) that has been proposed in previous work [10]. A technique to evaluate the single stitched laminates under pure shear loading was also confirmed. However, further works are still needed to obtain a better understanding of stitch bridging mechanism, particularly on the pre-crack process where the release films seem not work properly in the stitched laminates.

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